

Theory of translation in language learning

Eshboyev Ro'zimurod Toxir o'g'li

Student of Termiz state university

Annotation: This article discusses the role and importance of translation theory in language learning, and includes a lot of information on translation theory.

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Along with other performance-based disciplines, translation has both a theoretical and a practical core. There is an unresolved friction between theoreticians and practitioners. Translation is taught as an academic or professional competence at undergraduate and postgraduate level, while translation studies encompasses the research and theoretical investigation of the subject. The theory of translation, or translation theory, previously the denomination of the whole field, is now usually a subset of the discipline. Multiple theories have evolved, and there is no formal consensus. Each theory reflects a different approach to the practice and study of translation.

Questions of theory delve into the fundamentals of a field: what a theory of it is, how theory can be applied and how different theories interact. Translation of some sort must have been in existence since the invention of language, yet until the middle of the twentieth century relatively few translators had received formal training. In such circumstances, what 'formal' theory existed was generally limited to impressionistic, philosophical or religious commentary located in some paratext of the translation, in a preface or other foreword or afterword. Even attempts at more systematic writings, such as [Reference Dryden, Schulte and Biguenet Dryden's \(1680\)](#) or [Reference Tytler and Robinson Tytler's \(1797\)](#), did not go much further than identifying certain translation strategies and selecting various translation solutions. The nineteenth-century German Romantics such as Goethe, Schlegel and Schleiermacher trod a different path through the hermeneutic world, [Reference Schleiermacher, Schulte and Biguenet Schleiermacher \(\[1813\] 1992\)](#) devoting a public lecture in 1813 to discussing different methods of translation.

Translation theory is the scientific and critical study of the views, opinions, observations, and colorful experiences associated with the broad living practice of translation, explaining the rules and principles, their boundaries and norms. Translation

as a concept represents: scientific and practical process; results of scientific-practical process (translation of works of great writers); translation is a science, a subject.

The first theoretical ideas about the theory translation originated in ancient Rome. Aristotle, Cicero, and Horace, who were fluent in Greek and Latin, argued that words should not be followed in the translation process, but that their meanings should be weighed first and then translated. Later, Bartholomew and Manetti in Italy, du Belle and Malerb in France, Bacon and Dryden in England, Goethe and Humboldt in Germany, and Lomonosov and Sumarokov in Russia expressed their theoretical views on translation. In our country, the theory of translation as an independent philological science began to take shape mainly in the 50s of the twentieth century, but the practice of translation has a history of several thousand years. It should not be inferred from this idea that translation has evolved without theory for thousands of years. Our translators, who have translated many scientific, historical, political, religious, philosophical, and artistic books from English, Arabic, Persian, Indian, Azerbaijani, Turkish, and Russian into their own languages, are known translators who have been accepted and followed for centuries, based on their beliefs and rules.

The main goal of translation theory is to identify ways to translate several types of texts. The theory informs about how to choose appropriate version for presented text and gives information about different ideas views of scholars. It provides with information on general, natural, and individual topics of translation theory and culture. The basis of the theory is process of translation, different works and texts for translation. Many scholars consider that there are various problems in translating, such as problems with culture, with lexic, difficulties in grammar and etc. In grammar language consists of different cultural outcomes (genders of inanimate objects), application forms (Mr., Mrs.). The more language becomes a special phenomenon (flora and fauna) and serves for cultural purposes, the more problems will appear in translation. One of the most difficult problems in process of translation is finding the lexical equivalent of an object or event. The interpreter not only compares two languages, but also their cultures are taken into consideration. Because of difference within cultures, translator cannot find appropriate lexical equivalent in the case of translating geography, customs, beliefs and so on. The first problem in grammar is that it is not possible to translate accurately. The meanings and grammatical structures of words in languages are usually will not be the same. Let's take the word "logos" as an example. We can't find any equivalent word in English. This word means: "word", "content", "discussion" and etc. Interpreter should choose one of them according to the

situation. Moreover, there are problems with tenses in translation. The present tense, which is the same in most other languages, but in English there are two: "I go; Я иду" means "I go / I am going" in both forms. There are full of problems in pronouns too.

In short, translation theory introduces the basic principles and activities of translation schools. This improves translation skills. It allows you to learn a foreign language perfectly and to identify the differences and similarities between them when comparing the native language with a foreign language. When it comes to problems, sometimes for translator it is impossible to find clear equivalent. That's why he or she should understand real meaning of the word and try to describe it appropriately. In this case, a translator should find new ways and methods to express concepts.

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